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Methods of Virtual Reality Therapy for Overcoming Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder in Different Categories of Patients

Post-traumatic stress disorder is a complex mental disorder that arises as a result of extreme traumatic events and is usually accompanied by recurring and painful memories, emotional hyperarousal, and the avoidance of situations that remind one of the trauma. The symptoms characteristic of this disorder can disrupt the psycho-emotional state for a long time, markedly impair everyday functioning, and significantly reduce quality of life. Virtual reality is considered a promising method for overcoming post-traumatic stress disorder because it makes it possible to create safe, controlled scenarios for the gradual immersion in traumatic experience. The immersion technology helps avoid excessive psychological strain and gradually reduce emotional reactivity. Owing to its flexibility, the virtual reality environment is easily adapted to the needs of different categories of patients and can be combined with traditional approaches, in particular with psychotherapy and pharmacotherapy.

Neurobiological research confirms the substantial influence of virtual reality therapy on key brain structures involved in the formation and maintenance of post-traumatic stress disorder. In particular, virtual exposure reduces the activity of the amygdala, which is responsible for processing fear and stress reactions, and also promotes the regulation of the prefrontal cortex, which plays an important role in the cognitive control of negative memories [4]. In a meta-analysis that included three hundred and eight respondents, it was found that graded virtual reality exposure has a statistically significant large effect size (Hedges's $g = 1.10$, $p = 0.001$) in reducing symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder. At the same time, in groups with traditional virtual reality therapy, no substantial differences were recorded compared to the control [5]. Some clinical case reports demonstrate that after fourteen virtual reality sessions, the decrease in the score on the Clinician-Administered Post-traumatic Stress Disorder Scale can exceed twenty points, which correlates with a reduction in the intensity of traumatic memories and emotional reactivity.

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Separate studies describe even more striking results (in particular, a decrease on the Clinician-Administered Post-traumatic Stress Disorder Scale from seventy-nine to zero in an isolated case), although this requires further confirmation on a larger sample [6].

Neuroplasticity plays an important role in brain recovery, especially in disorders associated with trauma. Post-traumatic stress disorder is often accompanied by negative changes in the hippocampus, a structure involved in memory consolidation. Regular virtual reality sessions stimulate the gradual re-experiencing and re-evaluation of traumatic events, which can improve the functioning of the hippocampus and form new neural connections necessary for effective emotional regulation [5].

Personalized virtual reality therapy protocols make it possible to precisely adjust the level of stimuli and the duration of sessions, which is especially useful for patients with different experiences of traumatization. Combat veterans belong to one of the most vulnerable categories: modeling combat zones and the gradual approach to triggers help them to process traumatic memories in a controlled manner. A systematic review that analyzed eleven studies with a total of six hundred and forty-one participants (aged eighteen to sixty-two years) showed a positive effect of virtual reality therapy on the reduction of post-traumatic stress disorder symptoms. The average duration of a virtual reality session was about seventy-six minutes, and the total number of sessions ranged from three to twenty. The results varied depending on specific protocols and the level of personalization; however, the overall trend was positive [8]. When working with victims of violence, the emphasis is placed on creating safe virtual scenarios in which the intensity of triggers can be controlled [1]. Formats adapted for children and adolescents are also being studied, in which game elements and gradual exposure are added [10].

Combining virtual reality with traditional therapeutic methods makes it possible to enhance positive changes. Virtual reality exposure within the structure of cognitive-behavioral therapy helps simultaneously to “live through” traumatic memories and to reframe them in safe conditions [2]. According to some data, such integration can be more effective by thirty to thirty-five percent compared to ordinary exposure therapy. In combination with biological feedback, patients receive information about their own heart rate or electrodermal activity, which makes it possible to learn to manage stress reactions in real time [7]. The potential of pharmacotherapy is being studied separately: the use of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors in parallel with virtual reality can accelerate the reduction of anxiety and depressive manifestations [9]. There are also small studies on the combination of virtual reality with cannabinoids, in which additional alleviation of post-traumatic stress disorder symptoms and improvement of sleep have been observed; however, such results require larger randomized studies [3].

In conclusion, virtual reality therapy can substantially alleviate the course of post-traumatic stress disorder by acting on key neurobiological mechanisms and ensuring precise exposure in controlled conditions. The most pronounced positive effect is achieved through the personalization of virtual reality protocols and the combination of virtual exposure with other treatment methods, such as cognitive-behavioral therapy, biological feedback, or pharmacotherapy. Further research should focus on determining the optimal duration of courses of virtual reality sessions, on developing new technological solutions, and on a deeper study of neuroplastic processes that ensure a stable therapeutic result.

References

1. A randomized controlled trial to pilot the efficacy of a computer-based intervention with elements of virtual reality and limited therapist assistance for the treatment of post-traumatic stress disorder / M. Meggelen et al. *Frontiers in Digital Health*. 2022. Vol. 4. P. 1-16. URL: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdgth.2022.974668>.
2. Celebi B. Psychotherapy of post-traumatic stress disorder in the context of process and outcome studies. *Novel Forensic Research*. 2022. Vol. 1. P. 18-25. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5455/nofor.2022.08.04>.
3. Combining Cannabidiol with Prolonged Exposure Therapy for PTSD: Design and Methodology of a Pilot Randomized Clinical Trial / C. Straud et al. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*. 2023. Vol. 19. P. 114. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1017/cts.2023.421>.
4. Eskandar K. O impacto da terapia de exposição à realidade virtual no tratamento de TEPT e transtornos de ansiedade. *Artigos de Revisão*. 2024. Vol. 14. P. 1-21. URL: <https://doi.org/10.25118/2763-9037.2024.v14.1319>.
5. Heo S., Park J.-H. Effects of Virtual Reality-Based Graded Exposure Therapy on PTSD Symptoms: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*. 2022. Vol. 19. P. 1-10. URL: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192315911>.
6. Nie X. Research on the effectiveness of VR technology in assisted rehabilitation of PTSD patients. *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Virtual Reality, and Visualization*. 2021. Vol. 12153. P. 217-221. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2626655>.
7. Orakpo N., Vieux U., Castro-Nuñez C. Case Report: Virtual Reality Neurofeedback Therapy as a Novel Modality for Sustained Analgesia in Centralized Pain Syndromes. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*. 2021. Vol. 12. P. 1-5. URL: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2021.660105>.
8. Vianez A., Marques A., Almeida R. S. D. Virtual Reality Exposure Therapy for Armed Forces Veterans with Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder: A Systematic Review and Focus Group. *Int. J.*

Environ. Res. Public Health. 2022. Vol. 19. P. 1-16. URL: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19010464>.

9. Zhang M. PET+EMDR+VR to Reduce PTSD Symptoms. *Journal of Psychology & Behavior Research*. 2020. Vol. 2. P. 39-48. URL: <https://doi.org/10.22158/JPBR.V2N2P39>.
10. Zhao C. A novel treatment program for adolescents with post traumatic stress disorder with virtual reality technology. *Applied and Computational Engineering*. 2023. Vol. 3. P. 18-22. URL: <https://doi.org/10.54254/2755-2721/5/20230517>.